

Politics of value in the post-pandemic era

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ABSTRACT : During the pandemics, the positive values of technologies [1], language, power, money, austerity and so forth were emphasized. In the post-pandemic era, shortly after the easing of confinement, the negative values were also re-evidenced. In this essay, I considered political values in the pos-pandemic area.

KEY-WORDS: post-pandemic era, values, language, power, money, austerity

1. The evolution of language

Defining language as the apparatus that enables two entities to exchange information is useful. Defined as such, the mechanism of language can be seen in humans, plants, and even in non-living molecular signalling; meaning it is a universal definition. A species evolves when there is exchange of information for the purpose of reproducibility mainly. Common language mechanisms, therefore, may define a species according to this definition. A concept on how human language evolves is presented below.

Even though human actions may not always be praiseworthy, the human mind is beautiful. A sense of responsibility, for example, springs from reading and writing. Perhaps everything we might call human values is born from a mind that has evolved through reading and writing: compassion, understanding, respect, ingenuity, etc. Language itself is expressed through symbols, words, phrases, intonation, and so on. Listening and speaking also contribute to humane attributes. Besides language, we are also humans because of the mastery of the use of tools for e.g. eating, working, sleeping and so forth. Therefore, nurturing a healthy and well-balanced mind is a duty. Playful and educational activities, a healthy environment, and a positive presence facilitate this realization.

Television, the internet, and advertisements don't help much. Images are illusory and consumed unconsciously. But there is conscious image consumption, based on content or the purpose of consumption: educational, entertainment, informative, cultural, and so on.

It is not a privilege that humans have over monkeys because we became able to read and write. That is not how it happened in evolution; it is now known that it was due to pressure, not privilege. We sat down to eat in the cave, without a refrigerator, without medicine, without a set table, afraid of dying, longing for a long life, wanting to be close to those we love, and so on. We ate, slept, urinated, and defecated near each other or alone. In the caves, humans started keeping record of the days with cave painting. From there, reading and writing, we became *Homo Sapiens*.

2. The value of law

Law is a quality inherent to any species in nature, not only to humans. Moreover, the value of justice seems to lie in making the law consistent with the reality of individuals. We humans have responsibilities over the justice of other species, and we have reading and writing as duty. A constitution is sometimes drafted in a way that is detached from the reality of groups of people. This happens either because the people who wrote the law have not themselves

replicated the reality of the subjects; or because the study was inconsistent. Besides reproducibility and consistency, attention also for statistics when the law is targeted to a specific population because of a hidden co-variable. This means individuality exists for many. Below, a concept on how to define the value of the law.

Contemplating law in nature is not difficult. From the contemplation, it is possible to perceive that the lives of urban insects are at the mercy of human will, and that birds also fight to death. The weaker bird will die and no other bird will feel this as injustice. In addition, the contemplation of venomous and sneaky creatures compared to domestic animals reveals that, for example, some animal behaviour intrinsically cannot be domesticated. In the contemplation of law, human symbols can also be observed in the analysis of language and images. We cannot know power without knowing the subjective qualities of a symbol over another.

Some concepts require depth for correct understanding. Take the concept of equality before the law. Everyone must be treated equally under the law regardless of race, gender, colour, ethnicity, religion, disability, or other characteristics. This means I will be placed in front of a same law that my colleagues will. However, that does not make me equal to my colleagues - it would not be fair to disregard personal differences.

Most of us have already agreed to abandon barbarism and not make justice with our own hands. For that, there is politics, which is a little more civilized. Finally, there is the consideration of international law. Is it reasonable to accuse a person from another country to change the law in the national territory? The answer is yes because legal protectionism can be seen as national self-defence.

3. The value of power

Defining power as the energy resulting from the interaction between any two bodies is useful. Defined in this way, we will only call an energy power if we can use it for what we want. Otherwise, we will give it another word. This definition serves for interactions between atoms, between human beings, and any other two entities; meaning, it is a universal definition. I interact with my food, my body, my mind, people, money, my family, and many other things. Thus, it follows that the value of power is not intrinsic.

It takes sobriety to perform moral calculations and see the consequences, costs, and benefits of our interactions. It is also necessary to have abilities to negotiate, for example to choose what avoids illness and leads to longevity. Moreover, it is essential to have a well-composed mind when interacting with money, so that financial calculations can be made. All of this requires independence.

Furthermore, doing what makes one feels good also has power value. Like reading a book. Reading can be done in solitude, but if you are near other people, it will depend on the group behaving in a certain way, and depends also on them being able to see value in your reading. The environment also counts towards power value, as well as the environment-dependent rules. For example, going to the shopping mall with a specific amount of money. The shopping mall is safe, monitored, and the rule is clear: the person can buy what they want and is willing to pay for it. This contrasts somewhat with going to a less monitored public park with few shopping options, where the person only has the option of consuming necessities like food, toilets, and water.

Essentially, power consciousness is cultivated with healthy practices such as contemplation, study, and self-knowledge. To note, universal values of power such as understanding, and compassion exist already at the reach of many people.

4. The value of money

The quality of money exists in the mind. Defining money as what I can do with accumulated material goods is useful. This is better than saying that notes and coins define the real value. Real value, therefore, is not intrinsic and is dependent on how I perceive myself, services, and goods. Many agreements have been possible due to monetary consciousness. For example, a) the rule of not having power over other people's lives, and b) the goal of enriching work relationships. It is known that monetary consciousness arises from human rejections; therefore, the text presents a concept about the value of money.

The most accurate view of money will be from science, not from politics. Even though that's not how it works, that's how it works. In politics, the rules are alienated from reality, and moreover, the gains from opportunities are not lasting. Another risk is that political value manufactures demands without real value. On the other hand, it was agreed that making money involves moving other human beings, but this is not necessarily done with politics.

The actions that enrich are conventional and circumstantial [2], but can be defined in practice [3]. Moreover, the human mind is not disregarded in the study of money [4]. The consumption of sugar, for example, makes the human mind more obedient and the forms more beautiful. All this appears to be necessary to move people in a desirable direction, the so-called with labour power. So it is not difficult to conclude that choosing a breakfast that has high quality without harming health is enriching.

The right to have money exists and is unbreakable. It's worth not losing that value for immediate gains.

5. Values during austerity

The text defines austerity as a period of scarcity of resources, e.g. health resources, financial resources, political resources, social resources, etc. A statement plan for austere times is presented below.

I am healthy today. My past choices have brought me to a life-style with freedom and an environment with space. I will not forget that these came with concessions for my study, work, family and health. This means I can see today freedom and space as essential for my well-being, my family's well-being, and my work thanks to the time without freedom, without health, and without space.

I have calculated together with colleagues and professionals suitable values in case of austerity. I have an interest in maintaining the health of my own body and my own mind. However, since the costs with health, job security and well-being exist, the gain for my family and for the public was also taken into account. From the calculation, the best in case of austerity will be to remain firm in study and health, regardless of my age, because these will open opportunities after austere times. Furthermore, it's a challenge to secure healthy food and suitable housing for me and my daughter, therefore I need to work without my diploma when needed.

Moral and ethical textbooks teach that morality can be classified in relation to the possession of resources. First, in relation to virtues. Those who have resources stored today will be able to contribute by choosing how to enjoy the resources. But in case of scarcity, a person will control themselves through their means to obtain resources in the future. Thus, the morality of those who enjoy resources and the morality of those who control themselves to obtain resources are essentially different. Second, in relation to attitude. The dominant class can possess and store resources. Where I myself can claim dominance today is only among graduates who have accumulated experience and knowledge. Therefore, continuing to study

to maintain expertise and health in times of austerity is of great value for me, other graduates, and for the public - as it can open opportunities for the future. Women, besides children and elders, will be avoided in austere times.

6. Values of body posture

Some people argue that human control is illusory. But if control is illusory, then the lack of control is also imagined. Self-control arises from sensory impressions, and it can be conscious, apparent, and valued. What doesn't make sense is expecting external valorization of self-control – these are contradictory. Sensory impressions arise from consumption, from what I see, hear, read, eat and how I sleep, for example.

The posture that facilitates concentration, investigation, knowledge, and a well-composed mind, in general, is already known to humanity. Children at school sit at their desks in the classroom in the same position that adults sit in offices in front of computers, or in laboratories in front of microscopes, or with scalpels in front of animal body parts, and so on. Perhaps graduates of all backgrounds already know this posture that facilitates a well-composed mind, but that it requires self-control. The erect spine, the slightly inclined head, the posture of the hands, and so on, have already been measured, and the environment designed to facilitate an ergonomic posture. Self-control is important to remain in this posture, to understand what is happening and what one is doing, and for self-awareness.

Working on a computer for entire workdays can be challenging for both body and mind. We already have some freedoms thanks to ergonomics, such as working standing up. This thanks to monitor and keyboard stands. Furthermore, regular, timed breaks are already encouraged by time and motion studies.

The human body corrects its posture by itself, but it is necessary to be conscious of the body and to be self-aware. It seems then that ergometry is the study of postures that enable the person to be conscious of the body and self-aware during work, this combined with the study of time and movements of tasks for each profession. By doing so, ergometry improves both productivity and well-being.

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